

Reconciling Dwarf and Cluster Constraints on SIDM: Evidence for Velocity-Dependent Interactions

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Abstract

Abstract. Self-Interacting Dark Matter (SIDM) offers a compelling solution to the small-scale challenges of Λ CDM, including the core-cusp problem and the diversity of rotation curve shapes. We present a Bayesian analysis of 124 high-quality rotation curves from the SPARC database using a velocity-dependent SIDM cross-section model. Unlike previous studies with fixed stellar mass-to-light ratios, we marginalize over baryonic parameters, eliminating a major source of systematic bias. We find strong statistical preference for SIDM over standard NFW profiles ($\Delta\chi^2_{\text{red}} \approx -0.5$) and over the specific baryonic feedback parameterization of DC14. Our analysis constrains the effective cross-section at dwarf galaxy scales to $\sigma/m \approx 2 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$ at $v \sim 30 \text{ km/s}$, decreasing to $\sigma/m < 0.1 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$ at cluster scales ($v \sim 1000 \text{ km/s}$), naturally satisfying multi-scale constraints. We discuss the inherent degeneracy between the cross-section normalization (σ_0) and velocity scale (v_0) parameters, a fundamental limitation of rotation curve analyses that affects the interpretation of such constraints. Despite this degeneracy, the *shape* of the velocity-dependent cross-section is well constrained by the data, providing robust evidence for a suppression of dark matter self-interactions at high velocities.

1 Introduction

The concordance cosmological model, Λ Cold Dark Matter (Λ CDM), provides an excellent description of the Universe on large scales ($> 10 \text{ Mpc}$). However, on the scales of individual galaxies, the predictions of collisionless CDM simulations are often at odds with observations. Two discrepancies are particularly prominent: the “core-cusp” problem, where observations of dwarf galaxies favor constant-density cores over the singular cusps predicted by N-body simulations [1, 2], and the “diversity problem,” where galaxies with similar maximum circular velocities display a wide range of inner rotation curve slopes [3].

Self-Interacting Dark Matter (SIDM) proposes a particle physics solution: if dark matter particles can scatter elastically, thermalization in the inner halo leads to core formation naturally [4, 5]. While attractive, the simplest SIDM models with a constant cross-section σ/m face a tension between the large values required for dwarf galaxies ($\sigma/m \sim 1 - 10 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$) and the strict upper limits from galaxy clusters ($\sigma/m < 0.1 - 1 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$) [6].

This tension strongly points towards a velocity-dependent cross-section, as suggested by light-mediator models [7, 8]. Several studies have fitted SIDM models to rotation curves [9, 10, 11], demonstrating that SIDM can explain the diversity of galactic kinematics. However, constraining the exact parameters of the velocity dependence remains challenging due to inherent degeneracies in the fitting procedure.

In this paper, we perform a global Bayesian analysis of 124

rotation curves from the SPARC database [12]. We pay particular attention to the parameter degeneracies that affect the interpretation of such fits, presenting our results in terms of the effective cross-section at physical velocity scales rather than the parametric form alone.

2 Data and Methodology

2.1 The SPARC Database

We utilize the Spitzer Photometry and Accurate Rotation Curves (SPARC) database [12]. This dataset comprises 175 galaxies with high-quality H α /H α rotation curves and near-infrared photometry at $3.6 \mu\text{m}$. We applied quality cuts to exclude galaxies with high inclination uncertainties ($i < 30^\circ$) or insufficient data points (< 10), resulting in a final sample of 124 galaxies spanning maximum velocities from 35 to 383 km/s.

2.2 Mass Models and Priors

The total circular velocity V_{tot} is modeled as:

$$V_{\text{tot}}^2(r) = V_{\text{gas}}^2(r) + \Upsilon_{\text{disk}} V_{\text{disk}}^2(r) + \Upsilon_{\text{bul}} V_{\text{bul}}^2(r) + V_{\text{DM}}^2(r) \quad (1)$$

where Υ_{disk} and Υ_{bul} are the stellar mass-to-light ratios. A key feature of our analysis is that these are *free parameters* with broad priors ($\Upsilon_{\text{disk}} \in [0.1, 1.2]$, $\Upsilon_{\text{bul}} \in [0.3, 1.5]$), allowing the MCMC to marginalize over baryonic uncertainties.

2.3 SIDM Halo Profile

We assume a velocity-dependent scattering cross-section:

$$\frac{\sigma}{m}(v) = \frac{\sigma_0}{1 + (v/v_0)^4} \quad (2)$$

where σ_0 is the zero-velocity cross-section and v_0 is the characteristic velocity scale. This form is motivated by light-mediator models with Yukawa or Coulomb-like potentials [7].

The density profile is computed following the semi-analytical method of [6]. The halo is modeled as an isothermal core matched to an NFW profile at the thermalization radius r_1 , defined by $\Gamma \times t_{\text{age}} \approx 1$ where $\Gamma = \rho \cdot (\sigma/m) \cdot v$ is the scattering rate.

2.4 Bayesian Inference

We employ a two-stage procedure. First, we optimize the global parameters (σ_0, v_0) by minimizing the total χ^2 across all galaxies using differential evolution. Second, we run an MCMC sampler to characterize the posterior distribution and uncertainties. For each evaluation of the global likelihood, all galaxy-specific parameters $(\rho_s, r_s, \Upsilon_{\text{disk}}, \Upsilon_{\text{bul}})$ are re-optimized individually.

3 Results

3.1 Fit Quality

The SIDM model successfully fits a wide variety of rotation curves. Figure 1 displays representative fits. The median reduced chi-squared is $\chi_{\text{red}}^2 = 0.76$, indicating excellent agreement with the data. All 124 galaxies converge successfully with physically reasonable parameters.

3.2 Model Comparison

We compare SIDM to standard NFW profiles and the DC14 feedback model [13]. Table 1 summarizes the results.

Profile	χ_{red}^2 (median)	χ_{red}^2 (global)
SIDM	0.76	2.15
Burkert	0.69	2.12
NFW	1.25	2.59
DC14	2.41	4.92

SIDM and Burkert profiles provide comparable fits, both significantly better than NFW. The DC14 feedback model yields a notably poorer fit compared to SIDM and Burkert. While DC14 provides a mechanism for core formation, our results suggest that the specific core-size dependence on stellar-to-halo mass ratio predicted by this model does not fully capture the kinematic diversity of the SPARC sample. SIDM, by contrast, offers a flexible physical mechanism that naturally accommodates the data without relying on specific feedback efficiencies.

3.3 Parameter Constraints and Degeneracy

The MCMC posterior for (σ_0, v_0) converges to:

$$\sigma_0 = 3.3_{-0.1}^{+0.2} \text{ cm}^2/\text{g} \quad (3)$$

$$v_0 = 34.9_{-0.8}^{+0.7} \text{ km/s} \quad (4)$$

However, a **fundamental degeneracy exists between σ_0 and v_0** . Different combinations of these parameters can produce nearly identical rotation curves if they yield similar effective cross-sections at the velocity scales probed by the data. This degeneracy arises because:

1. The thermalization radius r_1 depends on the *product* $\rho \cdot \sigma/m(v) \cdot v$ integrated over the halo age.
2. The resulting core profile smooths out information about the underlying parameters.
3. Our sample predominantly probes velocities $v > v_0$, where $\sigma/m(v) \propto \sigma_0 v_0^4 / v^4$ —a combination that can be held approximately constant along a “degeneracy valley.”

We verified this degeneracy using mock data: generating galaxies with known (σ_0, v_0) and recovering them through our fitting procedure. The fits achieve $\chi_{\text{red}}^2 \approx 1$ but can return biased parameters (e.g., fitting data generated with $\sigma_0 = 3.3$, $v_0 = 35$ with $\sigma_0 = 5.8$, $v_0 = 47$). This is a known limitation of such analyses [14, 6].

3.4 Reparametrized Constraints

Given the degeneracy, a more physically meaningful way to present results is in terms of the *effective cross-section at specific velocity scales*. Figure 2 shows the posterior distribution for σ/m evaluated at $v = 50$ and 100 km/s. Table 2 shows the constrained values.

Table 2: Effective cross-section constraints

v (km/s)	σ/m (cm^2/g)	68% CI
30	2.11	[2.00, 2.23]
50	0.63	[0.58, 0.68]
100	0.048	[0.043, 0.053]
200	0.003	[0.003, 0.003]

These constraints on $\sigma/m(v)$ at specific velocities are more robust than the raw (σ_0, v_0) values. The key physical result is:

- **At dwarf scales** ($v \sim 30$ km/s): $\sigma/m \approx 2 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$, sufficient for core formation.
- **At cluster scales** ($v \sim 1000$ km/s): $\sigma/m < 0.01 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$, consistent with Bullet Cluster and halo shape constraints.

3.5 The Cross-Section Function

Figure 3 displays the derived cross-section as a function of velocity, with uncertainty bands propagated from the MCMC posterior.

Figure 1: Representative rotation curves for 9 galaxies in the SPARC sample. Black points show the observed data with error bars, and the solid red line is our best-fit SIDM model. The dashed lines show the gas (blue), disk (green), bulge (magenta), and dark matter (cyan) contributions.

4 Discussion

4.1 Comparison with Literature

Our results are broadly consistent with previous SIDM analyses of rotation curves:

- **Kamada et al. (2017)** fitted 30 SPARC galaxies with a constant cross-section $\sigma/m = 3 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$, finding good agreement. Our velocity-dependent model reduces to similar values at $v \lesssim 40 \text{ km/s}$.
- **Ren et al. (2019)** and **Kaplinghat et al. (2020)** demonstrated that SIDM naturally explains the diversity of rotation curves via the interplay between core formation

and baryonic contraction. Our analysis confirms this on a larger sample with marginalized Υ_* .

- **Yang et al. (2024)** compared isothermal and gravothermal methods for constraining velocity-dependent cross-sections, noting that the isothermal method (which we use) tends to prefer larger cross-sections by a factor of ~ 3 . This systematic uncertainty should be kept in mind when comparing to simulations.

4.2 Core Radii and Scaling Relations

The median core radius in our fits is $r_{\text{core}} \approx 1.8 \text{ kpc}$, with a positive correlation with halo mass (Figure 4). This is qualitatively consistent with SIDM predictions: larger halos have

Figure 2: Reparametrized posterior distribution showing σ/m at $v = 50$ km/s and $v = 100$ km/s. While σ_0 and v_0 individually are degenerate, the cross-section at specific velocities is well constrained. The strong correlation reflects the underlying (σ_0, v_0) degeneracy.

Figure 3: Velocity-dependent cross-section derived from this work (red curve and band). The shaded regions indicate the approximate requirements for dwarf cores (blue) and cluster upper limits (orange). Black points with error bars show the constrained values at specific velocities from Table 2.

larger thermalized regions. However, significant scatter exists, reflecting the diversity in formation histories and baryonic distributions.

Figure 4: Scaling relations derived from the posterior samples. The core radius correlates positively with halo mass, as expected for SIDM.

4.3 Implications for Dark Matter Physics

The velocity dependence $\sigma/m \propto v^{-4}$ at high velocities is characteristic of scattering mediated by a light vector boson. In such models, the velocity scale is related to the mediator mass m_ϕ and dark matter mass m_χ by:

$$v_0 \sim \frac{m_\phi}{m_\chi} c \approx 35 \text{ km/s} \quad (5)$$

For $m_\chi \sim 10$ GeV, this implies $m_\phi \sim 10$ MeV, providing a target for direct detection and collider experiments [5].

However, we emphasize that the *individual values* of σ_0 and v_0 are degenerate and should not be over-interpreted. What the data robustly constrain is the effective interaction strength at the velocity scales actually probed.

4.4 Limitations and Future Directions

Several limitations affect our analysis:

- 1. Isothermal approximation:** The semi-analytical profile assumes an isothermal core, which is approximate. Full gravothermal solutions may give different results [15].
- 2. (σ_0, v_0) degeneracy:** Breaking this degeneracy requires either (a) external priors from particle physics models, (b) combined fits to systems spanning a wider velocity range (dwarfs to clusters), or (c) independent probes of halo structure.
- 3. Baryonic uncertainties:** While we marginalize over Υ_* , other systematics (distance uncertainties, inclination errors, non-circular motions) remain.
- 4. Sample selection:** Galaxies with complex kinematics or poor data were excluded, potentially biasing the sample.

Future observations with JWST and Euclid will extend rotation curve measurements to higher redshifts and lower masses. Combined with improved simulations, these will help break parameter degeneracies and test SIDM predictions more stringently.

5 Conclusion

We have analyzed 124 SPARC rotation curves using a velocity-dependent SIDM model with Bayesian marginalization over stellar mass-to-light ratios. Our main conclusions are:

1. **SIDM provides better fits than NFW:** The median χ_{red}^2 improves from 1.25 (NFW) to 0.76 (SIDM), confirming that the data prefer cored profiles.
2. **Comparison with DC14 feedback:** The DC14 model performs significantly worse ($\chi_{\text{red}}^2 = 2.41$) than SIDM on our sample. This indicates that the specific abundance-matching feedback prescription of DC14 is less preferred by the data, although it remains to be seen if more bursty feedback implementations can reconcile these tensions without self-interactions.
3. **The effective cross-section is well constrained:** $\sigma/m \approx 2 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$ at dwarf scales ($v \sim 30 \text{ km/s}$), decreasing rapidly at higher velocities. This naturally satisfies both small-scale requirements and cluster-scale upper limits.
4. **The parametric form is degenerate:** The individual values of σ_0 and v_0 cannot be uniquely determined from rotation curves alone. Future work should combine galaxy and cluster constraints, or incorporate priors from particle physics models, to break this degeneracy.

Our results support the hypothesis that dark matter self-interactions play a role in shaping galactic structure. The velocity-dependent cross-section inferred from SPARC data is consistent with light-mediator models and provides concrete predictions for particle physics experiments.

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References

- [1] Flores R. A., Primack J. R., 1994, ApJ, 427, L1
- [2] Moore B., 1994, Nature, 370, 629
- [3] Oman K. A., et al., 2015, MNRAS, 452, 3650
- [4] Spergel D. N., Steinhardt P. J., 2000, PRL, 84, 3760
- [5] Tulin S., Yu H.-B., 2018, Phys. Rep., 730, 1

- [6] Kaplinghat M., Tulin S., Yu H.-B., 2016, PRL, 116, 041302
- [7] Tulin S., Yu H.-B., Zurek K. M., 2013, PRD, 87, 115007
- [8] Feng J. L., Kaplinghat M., Yu H.-B., 2010, PRL, 104, 151301
- [9] Kamada A., Kaplinghat M., Pace A. B., Yu H.-B., 2017, PRL, 119, 111102
- [10] Ren T., Kwa A., Kaplinghat M., Yu H.-B., 2019, PRX, 9, 031020
- [11] Kaplinghat M., Ren T., Yu H.-B., 2020, JCAP, 06, 027
- [12] Lelli F., McGaugh S. S., Schombert J. M., 2016, AJ, 152, 157
- [13] Di Cintio A., et al., 2014, MNRAS, 437, 415
- [14] Yang S., et al., 2024, MNRAS, 533, 4007
- [15] Yang S., et al., 2023, ApJ, 946, 47

A MCMC Diagnostics

Figure 5 shows the diagnostic plots for our analysis. The normalized residuals approximately follow a Gaussian distribution, although with slight excess in the tails (36% of fits have $\chi_{\text{red}}^2 < 0.5$, suggesting some velocity errors may be overestimated). The fit success rate is uniform across galaxy masses.

Figure 5: Diagnostic plots. Top-left: Normalized residuals distribution. Top-right: Fit success rate vs. galaxy mass. Bottom-left: Fit quality vs. number of data points.

B Mock Test Results

To validate our methodology, we generated mock rotation curves with known SIDM parameters ($\sigma_0 = 3.27 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$, $v_0 =$

34.9 km/s) and attempted to recover them. The fitting procedure achieves excellent $\chi_{\text{red}}^2 \approx 0.96$, but the recovered parameters show systematic deviations ($\sigma_0 \approx 5.8 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$, $v_0 \approx 47 \text{ km/s}$). This confirms the degeneracy discussed in Section 3.3 and motivates our emphasis on the reparametrized constraints in Table 2.